

Near Field Characterization of an Imaging System based on a Frequency Scanning Antenna Array

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Abstract— This contribution describes the concept of frequency scanning for imaging applications. The designed frequency scanning antenna array, which works in Ku frequency band, is used for the sectoral illumination of the scene under investigation, enabling the recovery of information restricted to the selected area. While the proposed idea simplifies beam scanning techniques with respect to mechanical or electrically-controlled scanning systems, the price-to-pay is the limitation on the amount of scattered field information. The near field radiation of the frequency scanning antenna array is characterized through an equivalent source model to assess accurately the incident field used in the imaging algorithm. This analysis also enables the evaluation of the frequency steering performance of the antenna in the near field, validating its use for the proposed application.

Index Terms— Microwave imaging, Frequency scanning antenna array, Near Field characterization, Sources Reconstruction Method (SRM).

I. INTRODUCTION

THE growing interest in the inverse scattering methods [1]-[2] arises from the wide range of applications where non-destructive testing is required. Among these applications, medical diagnostics [3] or security scanners for the detection of concealed weapons [4]-[6], are of special interest.

Several recently developed electromagnetic imaging systems have introduced directive antennas that illuminate a spot of the Object-Under-Test (OUT), enabling the retrieval of information of the object, restricted to the illuminated area [7]-[9]. The complete image of the object is subsequently recovered using the information obtained from the different individually illuminated segments.

Several approaches have been proposed to achieve the required scanning of the illuminating source throughout the

object. Multiple mechanical solutions can be found in the literature, based on rotating mirrors combined, either with a linear movement [5] or tilt [6] of the probe, a rotary scanner with variable radius [7] or reflector antenna focusing systems with a mobile subreflector [8].

Nonetheless, for these scanning systems, the antenna array approach proposed in [9] may be more appropriate, as it enables the agile electronic steering of the illuminating source, leading to potential reductions of the acquisition time, which is generally a key factor in these imaging applications. However, these topologies require complementary variable feeding networks, along with the corresponding synchronized control circuitry, which may substantially increase the complexity of the associated acquisition equipment.

As an alternative to address this limitation, the use of a frequency scanning probe that can be directly controlled by the illumination frequency—without requiring any additional instrumentation—has been proposed in [10]. Using this approach, the acquisition set-up for a two-dimensional (2D) imaging system depicted in Fig. 1 is presented in this work.

Fig. 1. Proposed scattered field measurement set-up for object-under-test profile reconstruction purposes.

For the initial experimental validation of the described measurement set-up, the ten element frequency scanning microstrip antenna array presented in [10] has been chosen for the variable illumination of the object under test.

Due to mechanical restrictions of the positioners, the designed imaging system would require the Object-Under-Test to be placed in the near-field (Fresnel) region of the Tx antenna. The inversion technique presented in [11], which allows the use of multifrequency information, would be used to process the scattered field measurements from which the OUT profile would be recovered. Since this reconstruction algorithm requires a precise knowledge of the illumination conditions throughout the reconstruction domain, which lies

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within the near field region of the antenna, a thorough near field characterization at the different operation frequencies must be performed.

Two are the main contributions of the following work: first, the introduction of an acquisition set-up solely based on frequency scanning—without any additional steering control circuitry—for imaging applications, which is proposed to be tested in a further implementation of the imaging system. Second, a complete near field characterization of the frequency scanning antenna array radiated fields within the reconstruction domain is carried out, in order to validate its employment for the proposed imaging system. For completeness, the fundamental characteristics of the chosen antenna are briefly described.

Fig. 2. Concept of frequency scanning compared to fixed beam and beam scanning imaging systems. Top: definition of range and cross-range concepts [16]. Bottom: gathered range and cross-range information depending on the kind of imaging system. p_m denotes a generic angular beam steering position from p_0 to p_M , and f_n denotes a discrete frequency within the frequency bandwidth $f_0 - f_N$.

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the frequency scanning antenna array [10].

A. Frequency scanning for imaging applications

As indicated before, the aim of the frequency scanning antenna is its utilization in imaging applications. While frequency scanning is a well-known concept [12]-[14], its application for imaging has been hardly applied [15]. Imaging systems aim to recover the geometry of an object-under-test (OUT). In case of dielectric bodies, constitutive parameters may be also retrieved. Among different imaging systems

classification, one can be established according to the OUT illumination: i) fixed beam, in which the OUT is illuminated with the same beam for the entire frequency bandwidth, and ii) beam scanning, where the beam steering is modified, thus changing the OUT illumination [5]-[9]. Fig. 2 compares fixed beam and beam scanning systems, concluding that beam scanning can be interpreted as the combination of multiple fixed beam illuminations. Fixed beam (red squares in Fig. 2) provides just range information [16], i.e. the distance from the Tx antenna, while beam scanning provides both range and cross-range (angular position) [16] information (black dots in Fig. 2).

The main drawback of beam scanning systems is the need of mechanical or electrically-controlled phase-shifting systems to steer the antenna beam. The required beam steering control system is quite complex, and the scanning time can be increased due to the use of mechanical devices. Regardless of the system complexity, these solutions have been adopted in practical imaging systems (e.g. for concealed objects detection hidden under clothes [4],[8]).

Frequency scanning antennas provide a simpler and faster way to achieve beam steering capabilities, requiring neither active phase-shifters nor mechanical control of the beam [10],[12]-[14]. In terms of amount of information for imaging applications, frequency scanning can be seen as a trade-off between beam scanning (which provides both range and cross-range information) and fixed beam configuration (range information only), as depicted in Fig. 2 (blue squares).

II. ANTENNA ARRAY DESCRIPTION

The frequency scanning antenna array used in this work was originally developed as the far field illuminating source for a microwave imaging data acquisition set-up proposed in [10]. The main design features of the 10 element array topology, schematically shown in Fig. 3, are briefly described below.

A. Individual Radiating Element

The individual radiating element of the array is an aperture coupled microstrip antenna, designed in the multilayer substrate structure outlined in Fig. 3. The rectangular radiating patch is etched on a 0.75 mm thick Rogers 3003 substrate layer ($\epsilon_r = 3$ and $\tan \delta = 0.0013$ at 10 GHz), and placed inverted on top of a 2.6 mm thick foam layer ($\epsilon_r = 1.07$ and $\tan \delta = 0.0041$ at 10 GHz).

The patch is fed from underneath by electromagnetic coupling through a rectangular slot etched on the ground plane of the feeding network, which is structured on the bottom side of another 0.75 mm thick Rogers 3003 substrate layer. The multilayer structure is assembled using nylon screws.

Aperture coupling is advantageous over other feeding techniques for this kind of applications, as the feeding network is shielded behind its ground plane, limiting the impact of its spurious radiation on the main antenna radiation pattern.

The electromagnetic Method of Moments (MoM) simulation [17] of the individual radiator shows an impedance bandwidth ($|S_{11}| < -10$ dB) between 14 and 18.5 GHz.

B. Feeding Network

The frequency scanning antenna design used in this work is based on a phased array whose elements are fed through transmission line segments with different lengths. The phase shift undergone by an electromagnetic wave propagating through a lossless transmission line segment of length L , is known to be given by (1):

$$\Delta\phi = -\beta L = -\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_g} L = -\frac{2\pi}{v_p} fL, \quad (1)$$

where f is the operating frequency and v_p the propagation velocity in the transmission line. Thus, for a fixed transmission line length L , the phase shift $\Delta\phi$ is linearly dependent on the operating frequency. For the main beam to be pointed at the boresight direction at the center frequency $f_0 = 16.5$ GHz, the difference in electrical length between the feeding line of consecutive radiating elements must be an integer multiple of the guided wavelength at the central frequency λ_{g_0} , $\Delta L = N \lambda_{g_0}$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$. In order to achieve the desired steering range $\Delta\theta = 30^\circ$ in the frequency interval between 15 and 18 GHz, $N = 2$ was chosen for this design.

Fig. 4. Simulated scattering parameters of the feeding network versus frequency: (a) Amplitude and (b) phase.

The feeding network is based on a series topology consisting of a main delay line from which a fraction of power is successively extracted for each of the radiating elements, as outlined in Fig. 3. The transmission line segment between

consecutive elements must be $\Delta L = 2 \lambda_{g_0}$, leading to this characteristic meandering shape. The main delay line is implemented with a characteristic impedance of 90Ω which, due to its narrower width, considerably simplifies the layout of these hairpin bends.

The feeding signal for each radiating element is extracted from the main delay line through an asymmetric T-junction power divider, matched to 90Ω at its input. The divider is designed to deliver -9 dB of its input power to the 50Ω input port of each antenna element (9 dB tap loss).

The scattering parameters of the complete feeding network have been evaluated through a MoM electromagnetic simulation [17], using 50Ω reference ports. The transmission coefficients between the input (port 1) and each of the outputs $S_{1,n}$ are shown in terms of amplitude in Fig. 4 (a) and in terms of phase in Fig. 4 (b).

Fig. 5. Prototype of the frequency scanning antenna: top view (upper side) and bottom view (lower side).

Since identical power dividers have been used for all the output ports, the power delivered to each of them progressively decays between the first $|S_{1,2}| \approx -9$ dB and the ninth output $|S_{1,10}| \approx -19$ dB, while the remaining power is delivered to the tenth antenna element.

This progressive decay in the feeding amplitude brings about an increase of the radiation pattern secondary lobe level, together with a slight widening of the main lobe and a certain degree of null filling, with regard to a uniform amplitude distribution. Although this amplitude pattern could be mitigated through the individual design of the asymmetrical power divider for each of the output ports, the overall performance of the antenna is considered acceptable for this preliminary experimental validation of the system. As shown in Fig. 4 (b), the feeding network effectively provides a frequency dependent progressive phase shift distribution to the antenna array elements, leading to the desired frequency scanning behavior. An image of the manufactured prototype that has been used in this work is presented in Fig. 5.

III. ANTENNA ARRAY MEASUREMENT AND NEAR FIELD CHARACTERIZATION

The manufactured antenna array prototype has been measured at the spherical range in anechoic chamber (TSC-UNIOVI lab) [18]. The separation between the AUT (Antenna

Under Test) and the probe (horn antenna) is $R=5.15$ m. Given the AUT size $D=0.2$ m, the far field distance is $R_{FF} = 2D^2 / \lambda = 4.8$ m at the highest operating frequency (18 GHz), and 4 m at the lowest (15 GHz). Thus, it can be considered that the field has been measured in the far field region. A schematic diagram of the measurement set-up is shown in Fig. 6. The radiated field is measured on a spherical domain from $\theta = -90^\circ$ to $+90^\circ$, with $\Delta\theta = 0.5^\circ$, in the E-plane ($\varphi = 0^\circ$ according to the reference system definition). The measured frequency range covers from 14 GHz to 18 GHz with 200 MHz step.

Fig. 6. Antenna array measurement set-up.

Fig. 7. Reconstructed equivalent currents (amplitude and phase) on the antenna array aperture plane for different frequencies.

Fig. 8. Radiated field (copolar component) for different frequencies and distances.

A complete antenna radiated field characterization has been performed through the calculation of an equivalent current distribution [19]-[22]. From the measured electric field at a

distance of $R = 5.15$ m, an equivalent magnetic current distribution is reconstructed on a linear domain placed in front of the antenna array. The dimension of this domain is 0.4 m along the ‘x’ axis, covering the entire antenna array. The equivalent magnetic currents are reconstructed for all the frequencies.

Fig. 9. Calculated copolar and crosspolar components at $f = 16.5$ GHz. Near field ($R = 0.5$ m) and far field patterns.

Fig. 10. Near field (copolar component) at $R = 0.5$ m from $f = 15$ GHz to $f = 17.8$ GHz in 400 MHz steps.

Fig. 7 represents the amplitude and the phase of the reconstructed equivalent magnetic currents, which clearly show higher amplitude levels in the region where the antenna array is placed. Within these limits, the phase distribution shows a uniform slope, which is in connection with the working frequency.

From the reconstructed equivalent currents, the field at any point of the E-plane can be calculated. Thus, the near field at 0.5 m (distance in the proposed imaging system) as well as the far field has been calculated. As indicated in [19]-[22], the field radiated by the equivalent currents can be considered the same as that one radiated by the AUT. The measured field at $R = 5.15$ m is virtually identical to the calculated far field, as this distance corresponds to the antenna array far field region.

A detailed study of the near field/far field pattern is shown in Fig. 8, where the calculated pattern at $R = 0.5$ m and in the far field region are compared with the measured patterns at $R = 5.15$ m. The main lobe steering hardly changes when working in the near field region. Crosspolar levels are plotted in Fig. 9 for the working frequency of 16.5 GHz, showing that they are about 20 dB below the copolar component at the main lobe position.

The copolar field distributions at $R = 0.5$ m between 15 and 17.8 GHz have been magnified in Fig. 10. The secondary lobe

level is about -6 dB between 15 and 15.8 GHz, and a slight widening of the main lobe can be observed between 15.8 and 17 GHz. Although the presence of secondary lobes in the illuminating source may limit the overall precision of the reconstruction method, the performance of this antenna is considered sufficient for a preliminary experimental validation of the proposed imaging set-up.

Fig. 11 represents the far field pattern vs. the operating frequency, showing the scanning margin, which goes from +35° at 14 GHz to -15° at 18 GHz, providing a 50° scanning range. It can be observed that the behavior with the frequency is approximately linear, especially between 15 GHz (angle of +20°) and 18 GHz (denoted with a dashed white line in Fig. 11), with a 11.67 °/GHz slope or, equivalently, 1.167 °/100 MHz. This 3 GHz range was also the initial operation bandwidth of the designed antenna [10].

Fig. 11. Far field (normalized amplitude, dB) as a function of angular position (in degrees) and frequency (GHz).

Fig. 12. Near field (normalized amplitude, dB) at $R = 0.5$ m as a function of angular position (in degrees) and frequency (GHz). RFOD: Radiated Field Observation Domain (blue line).

The field calculated at 0.5 m is plotted versus frequency in Fig. 12. A well defined main lobe is still observed at this short distance, preserving the nearly linear steering behavior with regard to frequency, with the same slope as in the far field pattern. These results suggest that the studied antenna design could be used as the frequency scanning illuminating source for the proposed near field imaging application, at distances down to 0.5 m.

As indicated before, the main advantage of the antenna characterization by means of an equivalent magnetic current distribution is the possibility of calculating the radiated field at any point of the E-plane. Since the reconstruction algorithm

requires a detailed characterization of the illumination conditions in the reconstruction domain, the field distribution in the XZ plane ('z' varying from 0.1 m to 5 m, and 'x', from -2 m to 2 m) has been studied. The field distribution for several frequencies is plotted in Fig. 13, where the main beam steering is clearly visible. The antenna near field frequency scanning capability can be appreciated, even for a distance as short as 0.5 m. The crosspolar field levels, which are about 20 dB below the copolar components, are shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 13. Copolar component (normalized amplitude, dB) evaluated in the XZ plane for different frequencies.

Fig. 14. Crosspolar component (normalized amplitude with respect to the copolar component, dB) evaluated in the XZ plane for different frequencies.

Finally, the beam steering capabilities at the distance $z = 45$ cm are evaluated. This analysis is of interest for the design of the proposed imaging system based on the frequency scanning antenna. As stated in the introduction, the distance between the transmitting array (frequency scanning antenna) and the

object-under-test (rotation axis) will be 45 cm due to mechanical limitations.

The illumination produced by the frequency scanning antenna array can be effectively swept across the surface of the object under test: for each frequency, a different region of the object-under-test cross-section is illuminated. To illustrate this concept, Fig. 15 represents the field distribution on an object placed 45 cm away from the frequency scanning antenna array, with constant arbitrary profile along the 'y' axis, and for four different frequencies (it is assumed that the manufactured antenna array presents a sinusoidal amplitude distribution in the elevation plane, 'y' axis). In the interval between 15 and 18 GHz, the object can be illuminated with four different hardly overlapped beams, considering a -6 dB threshold.

Fig. 15. Incident field (normalized amplitude, dB) on an arbitrary-shape object-under-test placed 45 cm far from the Tx antenna array.

IV. CONCLUSION

A novel imaging set-up scheme based on a frequency scanning antenna has been presented. This approach enables a substantial simplification of the required equipment, leading to potential reductions of the acquisition time. For the practical implementation of this set-up, the near field radiation of an existing frequency scanning antenna has been calculated throughout the NF reconstruction domain, as it is required by the reconstruction algorithm. This analysis provides additional information about the frequency scanning capabilities of the antenna in the reconstruction domain. Further work will be focused on the proposed imaging set-up implementation and experimental validation with measurements.

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